

A Multiplier-based Analysis of the Indirect Impact of Non-Turkish International Tourists on the TRNC Economy

Huseyin Bozdoglar¹

¹*The American University, 99302, Cyprus (Northern)*

Abstract

Applying the generic input-output analytic process developed at the Michigan State University on the 460 respondents who made up the sample group, this study used multipliers to estimate that for every lira spent by international tourists in North Cyprus in the year under study, 0.35 kuruş of indirect secondary income was generated in secondary industries. Also the total (sampled) international tourist expenditure during the period under study was observed to indirectly create 6 secondary jobs in the secondary industries, which support the tourism industry.

Keywords: tourism, economic impact analysis, multiplier analysis, North Cyprus

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Introduction

This study is the second installation in a two-part study on the impact of international tourist expenditure on the economy of North Cyprus. The first part examined the direct impact of such expenditure on the economy using the input-output economic impact analysis. This part builds upon the findings of that study and seeks to examine across secondary industries related to the tourism industry, the subtle yet important indirect effects of international tourist expenditure on the economy of North Cyprus through the use of multipliers. Thus the major objective of this study is to provide more valid understanding of the phenomenon by expanding on the outcome of the input-output economic impact analysis of the impact of international tourist expenditure on the economy of Northern Cyprus by examining the multiplier effect. In order to better guide the objectives of this study, the following research question was posed: Applying an appropriate multiplier model, what is the indirect impact of the expenditure of international tourists on the economy of Northern Cyprus? It begins with a concise background review of the use of multiplier based analytic frameworks in economic impact studies and progresses to the generation of multipliers for use in the study followed by an application of these multipliers on the international tourist expenditure derived from the first installation of the study.

Multiplier-based Analytical Frameworks: A Historical overview

Imagine the total national economy of a nation as a sealed leather bag into which a measured dose of exogenous expenditure is injected. What overall changes in income will result? What overall impact or ripple effects will the introduction of these outside-originated spending have on the entire economy? These are some of the questions that multipliers seek to provide answers to. Originating from the early work of John Maynard Keynes, multipliers according to Bannock et al. (1972), are instruments used to measure the effect of a change in one or more constituent components of aggregate demand (for example government expenses, demand for a nation's exports and etc.) on the entire economy of a nation. As mentioned in the preceding paragraph, the concept of multipliers was first developed by John Keynes whose seminal work gave birth to the simple multiplier which have proven to be very instrumental and highly regarded in macroeconomic analytic studies (Saayman et al. 2000). However other early scholars including Chenery & Clark (1962), Miernyk (1965) and Richardson (1972) were believed to have been responsible for further refining and developing the concept. These scholars were among the initial researchers to have used input and output tables in their work with multipliers (James, 1999).

From a multiplier theoretical perspective however, it is important to acknowledge that up until the 30s, a vast array of multiplier theories had been generated including theories on the effect of leakages and related recommendations (Hall & Lew, 2009). However, Matias et al. (2009) makes it clear that it is important to note that the first comprehensive economic impact model which not only provided a general picture of the effect of the injection of exogenous expenditure on an economy, but provided a very detailed description of the direct and indirect effects of such an event on an economy; was the work of Khan, (1931).

Following Khan's, (1931) Keynes introduced the use of multipliers in analyzing macroeconomic related issues. Further development of the concept was carried out by other scholars prominent among which was the work of Samuelson (1939). However the conceptualization of the multiplier developed by Keynes has been the most enduring of all available formulations, and has been the foundation upon which modern and current multiplier theory was developed (Matias et al. 2009).

From a definitional perspective, the primary essence of a multiplier can be described simplistically by understanding that every event which is capable of introducing more expenditure into an economy irrespective of the source, will definitely "cause an increase in the level of income" in that economy irrespective of the size of the economy (James, 1999 p. 27). According to James, (1999, p. 27) the term multiplier can then be viewed as an expression of the "coefficient that shows the actual change in income resulting from some exogenous spending". Kaul (1985 p. 82) further describe it technically as "the number by which a change in expenditure must be multiplied in order to determine the resulting change in income". Matias et al.,(2009) However notes that the interpretation of the application of multipliers to economic impact analysis and the resulting outcomes obtained depends to a large extent on the category of multiplier being used. The next section presents an overview of the category of multipliers in common use among economic impact researchers in extant literature.

Categories of Multipliers

As mentioned in the section above, varying outcomes will be obtained from economic impact analysis depending on the category of multipliers adopted and applied. In other words, depending on how a multiplier is formulated, the computation of the income effect will yield varying results (Yacob et al. 2007). The multiplier formulation hence refers to the manner in which direct, indirect and induced income effects are made to interact with each other by a given multiplier (Dwyer, et al. 2012).

Bonn (2008), drawing from the work of Jackson (1986), presents two major categorizations of multipliers. They are the **orthodox** and the **unorthodox** income multiplier categories (James, 1999).

The orthodox income multipliers also referred to as the ratio multipliers (Archer 1982), are further subdivided into two sub-categories: Type I multipliers and Type II multipliers (Jackson 1986). They define Type I multiplier mathematically as the summation of direct and indirect income effects, divided by the direct income effect (Jackson 1986). On the other hand they define Type II multiplier mathematically as the summation of direct, indirect and induced income effects divided by the direct income effect (Jackson 1986 & James 1999). It is important to note that both Type I and Type II orthodox income multipliers have the direct income effects as the denominator in both equations, while the results of the formulation represents the value of 'k' the multiplier coefficient (Bonn, 2008).

Unlike the orthodox income multipliers, the unorthodox income multipliers also fondly referred to as the Keynesian income multipliers (Bonn, 2008;

Archer, 1982), does not relate its formulation to the direct income effect, but does relate its formulation to the amount of increased expenditure injected into the economy. In other words, in its formulation, the multiplier coefficient also represented by the letter 'K' is equal to the summation of the direct, indirect and induced income effects divided by the increased expenditure injected into the economy and represented by the letter 'E' (Bonn, 2008). James, (1999) notes that two of the most prominent scholars responsible for majority of the current developments in multiplier related methodologies Archer and Henderson, both favor the use of the Keynesian income multipliers or the unorthodox income multiplier, for the sole reason that it gives a "smaller" but "more useful" multiplier coefficient which is in his opinion "more relevant for policy applications" (Archer 1976, p. 72).

In 1974, Archer further expanded the multiplier methodological offering by providing multiplier formulations for calculating the impact of more specialized increased expenditure elements including sales or transaction multipliers, output multipliers, orthodox employment multipliers and unorthodox employment multipliers (James, 1999). As mentioned earlier on, understanding each of these multiplier categories is important for accurate interpretation of the outcomes they provide.

Further development of Multipliers

Hall & Lew, (2009) notes that over the subsequent years, further developments were made to Multiplier Analysis by way of expansion of the original formulations. One of the prominent developments was the Keynesian multiplier model. The Keynesian multiplier model however, has mostly been used to estimate multiplier models for regional income estimations and in an altered form has been used to estimate the

impact of expenditures emanating from tourism on regional economies (Dwyer, et al. 2012). According to Bonn, (2008), three basic techniques emanating from the Keynesian model has been identified as appropriate for use in studies focusing on the estimation of the economic impact of expenditures emanating from tourism. These include: the economic base multiplier model, the ad hoc Keynesian multiplier model and the input-output multiplier model (Archer, 1973). The economic base multiplier model is one which tries to understand the degree to which the growth and development of a particular region was dependent on “external” and “internal” markets from an income or employment perspective (Jamal & Robinson, 2009).

It approached this by segmenting the local or regional economy under study into two separate segments categorically divided into groups of firms which specialize in “servicing markets outside the region” and those “servicing firms within the region” (James, 1999 p. 32). One major advantage of this approach is that it is practically simple and uses only data that are publicly available irrespective of how small or large the area under study is (Saayman et al. 2000). However some of its disadvantages include the fact that a very subjective approach is adopted when distributing industry expenditure into markets within and without, and the general assumptions that all elements listed in markets within and those listed in markets without have an identical multiplier effect regardless of which individual industries they were taken from as well as the assumption that economic growth depends entirely or majorly on sales derived from exports (James, 1999). These and other problems greatly inhibited its usefulness and according to Archer (1997), more rigorous models such as the Keynesian ad hoc or input-output models are usually preferred (Bonn, 2008).

The Keynesian ad hoc multiplier model on the other hand is more rigorous than the economic base multiplier, and has always been a favorite of early studies focused on measuring the impacts of tourism on economies (Chowdhury, 2012). They particularly point researchers in the direction of how income and employments is basically generated at the different stages or levels due to the introduction of tourism expenditure into an economy (Bonn, 2008). A slight modification of the original Keynesian model, the Keynesian ad hoc model was developed by Archer (1977) to help obtain estimates of income multipliers most especially for the tourism industry. The model seeks to understand the level of income generated by the first tourism based expenditure in a particular location based on the recognizable patterns of consumption exhibited by residents of the area or locality under study (James, 1999). In contrast to the economic base multiplier model, the Keynesian ad hoc model is more rigorous in nature and demands the collection and analysis of a significantly substantial volume of data usually through the issuance of structured questionnaires and survey instruments (Moutinho, 2011). There has been a lot of adaptations of the varying forms of the Keynesian model in extant literature and this includes the works of Archibald (1967), Steele (1969), Lewes-Devon & Cornwall (1970), Henderson (1975), and that of Edwards et al. (1976).

Dwyer, et al. (2012) however explains that one shortcoming of both the Keynesian and economic base multiplier models is the fact that they both use aggregations from multiple industries as a basis for their analysis. The implication is that inadequate individual industry specific data and information is obtained every time both models are used in conducting economic impact analysis which requires the analysis of multiple industries (Saayman et al. 2000). Attempts at addressing these and other shortcomings were made by proponents of the input-output economic analytic model (James, 1999). Due to the fact that the input output framework is the methodology of choice adopted for this research work, an entire subsection of the literature review has

been created to address extant literature on the salient developments of this model (Yacob et al. 2007).

H₁: Every Lira increase in international tourist expenditure will impact supporting industries (indirect and induced) positively, increasing the amount of income and jobs generated by secondary industries which provide support services to the primary tourism industries.

H₀: Every Lira increase in international tourist expenditure will have no impact on supporting industries and no impact on the amount of income and jobs generated by secondary industries.

Secondary Data Collection: Data for Generating Tourism Multipliers

The first phase of this study involved collecting spending data which was used to determine the direct effect of tourism on businesses and household incomes directly servicing tourists. This second phase of the study on the other hand involves the determination of the secondary impact of tourist spending by way of estimating the indirect and induced impact on businesses and households operating in industries which provide supporting services to the industries which directly service tourists. In line with economic impact analytic tradition the secondary effects are often calculated or estimated through the application of multipliers derived for the particular region under study (Stynes, 1999). To be able to generate these multipliers, the researcher would have to source microeconomic data usually published by national statistics bureaus (Jamal & Robinson, 2009). These secondary statistical data usually contains some of the aggregate figures in terms of aggregate income, and employment figures related to touristic activities within a particular region (Dwyer, et al. 2012)

These figures in turn are used to compute multipliers for a particular region under study and applied to estimates of direct impact obtained from the first phase of the study to derive estimates of the indirect and induced impact of international tourist spending on the region under study (Stynes, 1999). The national statistical organization in North Cyprus responsible for the information needed to generate multipliers for North Cyprus is the TRNC State Planning Organization (SPO). The major source of the secondary data used was the Economic and Social Indicators for 2010 published by the SPO in July, 2012 and retrieved from the SPO website. Before discussing the information retrieved and how it was used to generate the multipliers, it is important to first of all provide a succinct over view of multipliers, their place in economic impact of tourism studies and then their use in this particular study.

Generating Multipliers

Multipliers have been dealt with to a large extent in the previous sections of this article. In this section the specific multipliers used in this study will be explained. First of all it is important to reiterate that multipliers are important tools in economic impact analysis useful for accurately taking a snapshot of the secondary impact of tourist spending in a particular region (Moutinho, 2011). Tourist spending can have secondary effects on a particular region through indirect and induced means (Chowdhury, 2012). The indirect impact of tourist spending on the economy of a host region reflects the alterations and adjustments in the amount and type of goods sold, jobs created or lost, and additional income generated or lost within the secondary industries providing a back-link network of supporting services to the primary industries (such as hotels and restaurants) which cater directly to the tourists (Dwyer,

et al. 2012). In other words measurements of indirect impacts deal with understanding the benefits secondary firms which provide the supply support primary firms such as hotels require to provide an average tourist with a night of accommodation and related services (Moutinho, 2011). The indirect impacts of tourist spending on a host region is often measured using a multiplier subgroup often termed the Type I multipliers (Chowdhury, 2012). According to Stynes (1999), a typical formula for measuring or estimating the indirect impact of tourist spending on a host community or region from a sales perspective is represented by the equation below:

$$\text{Type I Multiplier (for sales)} = [\text{DS} + \text{IS}] / \text{DS}$$

Where DS represents Direct Sales figures and IS represents Indirect Sales figures

A second aspect of the secondary impact of tourist spending on a regional economy is the alterations and adjustments in the volume of sales, propensity with which jobs are created or lost, and the amount of new income generated or lost from the region as a result of difference observable and recordable in the amount of spending carried out by resident households as a result of incomes earned or the lack thereof directly or indirectly from tourist spending in the touristic destination or region under study (Dwyer et al. 2012). This measurement is referred to as a measurement of the *induced impact* of tourist spending on an economy (Matias, et al. 2009). It is in effect a measurement which seeks to understand the chain effect of each unit of tourist spending on the income of workers who work in firms servicing tourists directly and those who work in firms providing support services to the firms who service tourists directly as well as how changes in these workers' income affect their spending habits in the regional economy under study and the subsequent effects of these spending activity on the generation of more sales and income for manufacturers, whole sales or retailers upon whose goods such expenditure are made, and by extension upon the general economy itself (Bonn, 2008).

According to Stynes, (1999), a typical formula for measuring or estimating the induced impact of tourist spending on a host community or region from a sales perspective is represented by the equation below:

$$\text{Type II Multiplier (for sales)} = [\text{DS} + \text{IS} + \text{InS}] / \text{DS}$$

Where DS represents Direct Sales figures and IS and InS represents Indirect and induced Sales figures respectively.

Now these multipliers serve to present researchers with a snapshot of the rate at which organizations and residents are willing to purchase products produced only within the host community, nation or region under study (Flecha, 2010). The appropriate use of multipliers can reveal snapshots of spending at different levels within the economy of a particular host nation (Chowdhury, 2012). The purchase of goods imported into the host community constitutes important sources of leakage of funds from the economy of the host community, and as such are not the focus of multipliers (Jamal & Robinson, 2009).

Reliable application of Multipliers

It is however very important for the economic impact researcher to take precautionary measures to avoid the overestimation of the secondary impacts of tourism as this has

been a common problem with most economic impact of tourism research. This problem usually arises as a result of first the faulty understanding of what multipliers truly are and how they function and a consequent erroneous use of the different types of multipliers that do exist (Moutinho, 2011). One of the most significant sources of error leading to overestimation of secondary impacts stems from the exclusion of those products produced outside the locality but purchased by visitors to the locality which mostly results from the misuse of state, national or regional multipliers especially in estimating the economic impact of a particular community (Saayman, et al. 2000). Another key avenue through which erroneously high multiplier values can be obtained is through the overestimation of the induced economic impact of tourism (Hall & Lew, 2009). These impacts are usually obtained by obtaining a model of typical spending patterns of the residents of the location under study and redistributing income generated from an estimation of direct and indirect impact of tourism to the host community (Chowdhury, 2012). Some of the major sources of error in this method are the assumption during such calculations that the average household spending will increase across all observable levels in the patterns identified as income increases, or that all income generated in every household would be spent in the local community or region (Bonn, 2008). The fact that as incomes increase, most households will tend to want to save more as well as the fact that portions of increased income which goes into pension, retirement or social security funding though recorded as income earned, may not be immediately spent and when they are actually disbursed might not be immediately spent in the local community under study (Stynes, 1999). Finally the assumption that workers working in a particular touristic location from which they earn income actually do reside and maintain families exclusively in the city or region where they work (Bonn, 2008). Factoring in some of these assumptions in estimating the size of the multipliers to use is very important for obtaining reliable multiplier size and for the reliable deployment of multipliers (Dwyer, et al. 2012).

To obtain an accurate multiplier size, it is important to consider some key determining elements. How big or small and how narrow or diverse the economy of the location, nation or region under study is will determine the size of the multiplier that will be obtained (Jamal & Robinson, 2009). In general, an economy within which a vast array of products are produced will usually have a multiplier with a high figure due to the fact that all of the inhabitants of the region in question do not have to source key products from outside the location under study (Chowdhury, 2012). The size of the area under study is also an important determining factor of the size of the multiplier to be obtained (Bonn, 2008). Generally, a region that covers a vast geographic space would logically have a higher multiplier value than a smaller area especially if that region in question serves as a hub for other adjoining smaller areas (Saayman et al. 2000). Other key determinants of the multiplier size are the economic characteristics of the individual economic sectors within the location under study as well as the year of study in question. In general, economic sectors characterized by labour intensiveness tend to have a high sized induced impact values but not a high sized induced impact value (Stynes, 1999). Due to the fact that the use of a singular multiplier in a particular study does imply the average value of all of the multipliers for each of the economic sectors contained within that nation (Matias et al. 2009). To obtain values with higher degrees of accuracy, it is important that multipliers appropriate to individual economic sectors are used especially when examining the economic impact of a particular sector on a particular location, nation or region (Bonn, 2008). Also in reference to the year a determinant of the size of a multiplier, it is important to note that as economic and price situations are usually dynamic and

change within different time frames, the size of a multiplier obtained within a particular year or time period will be different from the size obtained within another time period or year (Hall & Lew, 2009). It is thus important to ensure that the multiplier appropriate for the year a study focuses on is used in the analysis to obtain a more accurate result (Yacob et al. 2007).

In summary, according to Moutinho, (2011) locations, regions or nations which are sparsely developed economically should normally have a small multiplier size, while nations, regions or locations with a highly diversified and higher level of economic development will normally have higher tourism multiplier values. One final area of caution when using multipliers is in understanding the difference between a multiplier and an economic ratio (Flecha, 2010). While multipliers are used to measure indirect or induced secondary effects of an activity, economic ratios on the other hand are used to measure and depict the relationship between economic activities such as jobs and sales which are the most common economic ratios available (Chowdury, 2012). They measure the degree or extent to which the carrying out of one job can produce a particular amount of sales in a particular economic sector in a given time period. In essence it is a simple way of transforming recorded sales in a particular region in a particular duration into jobs (Stynes, 1999). This ratio is often obtained by dividing the aggregate number of jobs in a particular economic sector by the aggregate amount of sales recorded for that sector in a given period (Saayman et al., 2000). Other economic ratios available includes value added ratios, personal income ratios and property income ratios, total impact jobs multipliers and other similar multipliers (Hall & Lew, 2009).

Input-Output Model-Compliant Application of Multipliers

To avoid exaggerated economic impact estimation, it is important to ensure that multipliers are applied following in a procedure that is compliant with the input output model of economic impact estimation from which multipliers themselves are derived (Jamal & Robinson, 2009). One of the key importance in making this consideration when applying multipliers is for researchers to deal with spending carried out by final consumers in a way that differs significantly from business to business spending (Dwyer et al. 2012). In other words, when dealing with visitor spending measurements, it is important to differentiate between the aspects of the spending that accrues to the local retail outfit and the portion of the same spending that accrues to the manufacturing firm which actually produced the product (Yacob et al. 2007). From an input-output analytical perspective, the addition of margins enables the accurate breakdown of the amount paid by a tourist visitor into its component parts which reflect the portion of such a payment which accrues to the retailer, the wholesaler and the portions of it which covers the price paid for transportation and logistics as well as the portion which belongs to the manufacturer (Flecha, 2010). The amount spent by the purchaser and its subsequent components are represented in the following equation:

$$P_p = R_m + W_m + T_m + P_{rp}$$

Where: P_p = Purchasing Price; R_m = Retail margin; W_m = Wholesale margin; T_m = Transport margin; and P_{rp} = Producer price (Modified from Stynes, 1999).

It is important to separate each of these components while carrying out tourism impact estimations because if a product is not produced within the region under study,

then the producer price must not be allocated as a spending category retained within the region under study (Bonn, 2008). In that light it is important to include only the retail margin or in some cases where the wholesaler and logistics and transportation company is located in the region under study, their portions may be included in the spending category or direct sales for use in the impact analysis (Matias et al. 2009).

Summary of Applicable Multipliers and their Derivations

The multipliers adopted for use in the economic impact analysis of international tourists on the economy of North Cyprus are summarized in the table below. This table and its constituent derivations are derived from Stynes (1999) and adopted by Bonn, (2008). It shows the key multipliers and economic ratios applicable to tourism impact analysis and the formula for computing each of them. The type II sales multiplier for instance can be derived by dividing the total value of sales by the value of direct sales contained within it, the type II income multiplier is derived by dividing the total value of income generated by the tourism sector, by the value of direct sales. While the type II jobs multiplier is obtained by dividing the total amount of jobs generated by the tourism industry by direct sales. Economic ratio derivation formulas are also presented in the table below.

Table 1: Multiplier and economic ratio calculations

Total Multiplier Calculations

Multiplier	Formula
Sales II	Total sales/Direct sales
Income II	Total income/Direct sales
Jobs II	Total jobs/Direct sales
Income Multiplier II (Ratio)	Total income/Direct income
Jobs Multiplier II (Ratio)	Total jobs/Direct jobs
Capture rate	Direct sales/Total spending
Effective Spending Multiplier	Sales II x Capture Rate

Multipliers Generated and Applied in this Study

In light of the above discussion of multipliers and the procedure through which they are derived, this section provides an overview of the multipliers that will be applied in this study to generate the secondary (indirect and induced) impact of international tourism on the economy of North Cyprus.

It is important to reiterate that the secondary data from which the multipliers were generated were retrieved from data contained in the Economic and Social Indicator for 2010 document published by the TRNC State Planning Organization’s (The official economic statistics agency for North Cyprus) website. Using secondary data from the SPO database, the following multiplier values were derived for Northern Cyprus’s tourism sector to be applied at the second phase, to the economic impact analytical tool to generate the secondary impact (indirect and induced) impact of tourism on the economy of North Cyprus.

Table 2: Multiplier and economic ratios for North Cyprus

Total Multiplier Calculations		
Multiplier	Formula	Value
Sales II	Total sales/Direct sales	1.00
Income II	Total income/Direct sales	1.60
Jobs II	Total jobs/Direct sales	58
Income Multiplier II (Ratio)	Total income/Direct income	0.56
Jobs Multiplier II (Ratio)	Total jobs/Direct jobs	0.43
Capture rate	Direct sales/Total spending	84%
Effective Spending Multiplier	Sales II x Capture Rate	0.42

Results: Application of Multipliers and Economic Ratios for North Cyprus

Applying the formulas mentioned in the methodology section of this study, to economic data retrieved from the SPO database, the following multipliers and economic ratios in Table 3 were determined for the TRNC economy for 2013.

Table 3: Multipliers and economic ratios for North Cyprus

Table 3. Multipliers & Ratios for North Cyprus (From an I-O model)

Sector	Direct effect ratios			Total effect multipliers		
	Income/Sales	Jobs/\$MM Sales	Sales I	Sales II	Income II/ Sales	Jobs II/ Sales
Lodging	0,34	23,0	1,40	1,70	0,60	33
Restaurant	0,35	31,0	1,38	1,66	0,57	39
Grocery production	0,15	5,3	1,37	1,54	0,34	12
Gas & Oil refining	0,05	0,6	1,30	1,38	0,14	4
Recreation	0,35	31,0	1,35	1,65	0,60	40
Other manf.	0,26	9,0	1,32	1,56	0,46	16
Retail	0,51	28,0	1,17	1,52	0,70	35
Tourism multiplier (calculated)	0,36	26,6		1,67	0,59	36

Indirect and Induced impact

The previous sections have revealed the direct and total impact of international tourist spending on the economy of northern Cyprus. In this section the indirect and induced impact of these tourist spending will be merely deduced by subtracting the direct impact figures from the total impact figures as economic impact literature makes it clear that total impact is an embodiment of both primary (direct) and secondary (indirect and induced) impact on the economy. Table 4 below presents a summary of

the secondary (indirect and induced) impact of international tourist spending on the economy of Northern Cyprus.

Table 4: Indirect and induced impacts

Table 4. Indirect and induced impacts

	Sales	Income	Jobs
Total Impact	1,163,609 TL	416,958 TL	25
Primary (direct) Impact	700,891 TL	250,667 TL	19
Secondary (indirect & induced) Impact	462,718 TL	166,291 TL	6

It can thus be seen that the secondary impact of the total amount spent by the tourists within the study group on the economy of northern Cyprus is such that it yielded about 462,718 TL in additional sales in industries catering to the Northern Cyprus tourism industry serving as their suppliers, manufacturers and so forth (indirect impact) in addition to sales generated by expenditure carried out by employees who work for tourism companies who are in direct contact with and directly cater to tourists (induced impact). It also generated 166,291 TL in additional indirect and induced income as well as the indirect and induced creation of an additional 6 jobs in the Northern Cyprus economy.

Findings from the perspective of the hypothesis posed

H₁: Every Lira increase in international tourist expenditure will impact supporting industries (indirect and induced) positively, increasing the amount of income and jobs generated by secondary industries which provide support services to the primary tourism industries.

H₀: Every Lira increase in international tourist expenditure will have no impact on supporting industries and no impact on the amount of income and jobs generated by secondary industries.

Findings from the study showed that the additional direct sales recorded from international tourist expenditure led to the generation of a total of 462,718 TL of secondary (indirect and induced) sales, 166,291 TL of secondary income and created a total of 6 new jobs in the secondary tourism supporting industries. In other words, every Lira of international tourist expenditure in form of direct sales, generated 0.40 Kurus of sales, 0.35 Kurus of additional income in the secondary industry providing supporting services to the tourism industry. Once again the above findings demand the rejection of the null hypothesis for the hypothesis generated.

In summary, it can be observed that international tourist expenditure has a significant impact on the economy of Northern Cyprus in terms of income generation and employment having positive effects on the primary and secondary industries alike. This is corroborated by the works of Wang et al. (2006); Laesser and Crouch (2006) as well as Mehmetoglu, (2007).

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